

ON THE LINGUISTIC STUDY OF ANTHROPNYMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8340629>

Abstract. *A certain amount of research work has been carried out on the study of anthroponyms in linguistics. In these studies, personal names related to the city of Kokand were considered, and some of them have now acquired toponyms. It is noted that the names of historical figures have been analyzed in the sources, although they are incomplete, and since the linguistic research on their formation has not been fully implemented, it is considered that a deeper scientific approach to it is necessary.*

Key words: *anthroponym, toponym, historical-linguistic wealth, historical person, khan, bek, biy, linguistics.*

О ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОМ ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНТРОПОНИМОВ

Аннотация. *По изучению антропонимов в лингвистике проведен определенный объем исследовательской работы. В этих исследованиях рассматривались личные имена, связанные с городом Коканд, некоторые из них теперь приобрели топонимы. Отмечается, что имена исторических деятелей проанализированы в источниках, хотя и неполны, а поскольку лингвистические исследования по их формированию не реализованы в полной мере, считается, что необходим более глубокий научный подход к ним.*

Ключевые слова: *антропоним, топоним, историко-лингвистическое богатство, историческая личность, хан, бек, бий, языкознание.*

Professor E. Begmatov is the first researcher of anthroponymic studies in Uzbek linguistics. After that, it should be noted that in the development of our linguistics, in particular, N.Okhunov, S.Koraev, G.Sattorov, S.Rahimov, S.Kenzhaeva etc. According to scholars, the names, nicknames and nicknames of a person, and the names of his parents, are not marked as place names based on the customs of Islam, and the fact that the names of Eastern scientists and scholars are not shown on the world map is a clear proof of this. Later on, the places that were converted into graves were named with the names of dear people, as a result of increasing the flow of pilgrims and economic benefits, and as a means of religious and legal protection.

It is known that the names were created by our ancestors many centuries ago and have come down to us as a historical-linguistic wealth, which has a huge cultural and spiritual value. Nowadays, anthroponyms are found as place names in almost all regions, and there are not a few that are given by the government's decision to perpetuate the names of people who are state, public figures, national heroes and cultural figures. Some historical sources also provide valuable information about the historical recognition of anthroponyms as place names. In particular, in this regard, it can be observed that the manual created by M. Ya. Dadabayev, dedicated to the toponymy of the ancient Khokandi Latif city, contains many noteworthy anthroponyms and information on the activities of these persons.

The fact that the "Davronbek" neighborhood, located in the southwestern part of the city of Kokand, is actually an anthroponym is a vivid example, as well as the fact that one of the main streets of the neighborhood is called Bobobek, also shows that the anthroponym has become a toponym. According to the author of the manual, Bobobek Tarkhan Haydarbek Otalik's son was

one of the great figures of the Kokand khanate. He served in the palaces of Umarmkhan and Muhammad Alikhan in the positions of "parvanachi", "kushbegi", "devanbegi". In return for his services, he was awarded the title of "tarkhan (free from taxes and duties)" and a large estate in this street.

The neighborhood that appeared on the site of Bobobek's estate is named after him. It is necessary to admit that S.Usmonova, a linguist who conducted research on the microtoponymy of the city of Kokand, touched upon the anthroponyms of the city, albeit briefly. The following descriptions are given in the stylistic work published on this matter. "A large part of the microtoponyms in the studied area was formed on the basis of personal names - anthropotonyms.. Many neighborhoods, neighborhoods and streets are named after the famous and respected people who founded the land, built it, owned it, spent money for its improvement, and were the leaders. Examples of this are the names of the places in the city called Khalifa Safo, Kitabdor Mirzo, Davronbek, Mulla Bashman, Khojibek, Valikhan Tora, Bekbotabek, Usta Bazar, Bobobek, Mirtohir, Mirzo Yodgor, Ashur Mirzo, Risqulibek, Sherali mingboshi, Muhammad Razzaq devanbegi.

In the study of anthropotonyms, it is of particular importance to identify the people who left their names to the places. We have managed to collect some information about the people and their activities that are the basis for toponyms based on historical documents and sources. In particular, Khalifa Safo was a student of the famous Bukhara sheikh Khalifa Husayn Bukhari and was considered one of the great religious figures of his time. He was the principal of the Jame madrasa in Kokand. He held the post of sheikhulislam in the khanate. He built a madrasa with his own money. The real name of the librarian Mirza is Mirza Ayyub, he served as the manager of the library in the Khan's palace during the reign of Kokand Khan Muhammad Ali khan. He was given the title of librarian.

Therefore, Mirza Ayyub became famous among the people under the name Kitabdor Mirza, he was also engaged in creativity, wrote poems and ghazals under the pseudonym Behjat, and compiled a divan. Davronbek is the son of Bobobek Tosaba, one of the great commanders of Kokand khan Khudoyar Khan. This person served as a military judge in the khan's army. During the Russian invasion, he participated in the defense of Shymkent, Tashkent, and Kokand. After the abolition of the khanate, he worked as a makhalla amin for some time. Mulla Bashman, who was considered one of the educated people of the city, served as imam in the neighborhood mosque where he lived. His services were great in the development of his daughter, the poetess Mahzuna, into a mature and virtuous person.

With the honor of independence, there is a need for a more in-depth study of anthroponyms whose names have been preserved in sources in the history of the city of Kokand and continue to serve for the restoration of history in a certain sense.

Probably because of this, the historian H. Bobobekov said: "The more you read and study history, the more you will read and search for it, especially to find new evidence on the unopened pages of history, on controversial, i.e. scientific, debatable events, and to look at these or other events of history in a new way. and must be evaluated. This includes the history of the Kokand khanate and the genealogy of its rulers. About one of such anthroponyms in "Anjum at-tawarikh" the real name of Narbo'tabek is given in full, and it is described in the section entitled "The mention of Abdulhamidbek ibn Abdurakhmonbek ibn Abdulkarimkhan, known by the nickname

Narbotur". According to Khudoyor khazoda, Abdulhamid khan, nicknamed Narbotur, lived in 1162/1747–1212/1797–98, and ascended the throne in 1177/1763. Norbutabiy subjugated the governors of Chust and Namangan as soon as he became the ruler. Norbotabi ends his career with the conquest of Khojand, for which he has to work hard. Only after Khudoyorbek's death, Kokand was completely united. Norbotabi marries Iriskul's cousin Mingoyim, and later has two sons (Alim and Umar) and a daughter (Aftaboyim).

Also, Norbotabi's eldest son Madamin from his first wife, three younger sons - Rustam, Pozil and Yodgor were born from unmarried wives, besides, he had four more daughters. Norbotabi appoints his brothers Shahruxhbi to Namangan, Khojibi to Khojand, his eldest son Madamin to Margilan (Yor Mazar), and his second son Olim to Torakurgan. Soon after Shahruxhbi died, Hajibi was appointed in his place. In 1797 (according to other sources, 1800), Madame became seriously ill and died. Norbotabi died in 1800/1801, after which his son Olim became the governor and continued to expand the Kokand region. He conquers Angren, Shymkent, Sayram, all of Tashkent region, important settlements on the caravan routes in Russia. Seeing that the state of Olim is now completely separate from others, it can fight against Bukhara, it is so strong, and accepts the title of khanate. His state is called the khanate of Kokand with its capital in the city of Kokand. During the period of Olimkhan, the political importance of Kokand increased. Olimkhan was a unique historical figure. He takes a number of measures to reorganize the religious foundation. For example, it abolishes "eshon", which is considered a religious title, and gives land and livestock to the poor, needy and "kalandar", while engaging them in socially useful work. He examines (tests) certain religious figures to see if they pray correctly and punishes those whose lies are exposed. They are dissatisfied with this behavior of Olimkhan. Using the fact that he is from Tashkent, they organize a conspiracy and spread false rumors that he was killed. His brother Umar will be installed on the throne. Olimkhan found out about the betrayal and left for Kokand by a short route, and an ambush was laid on the way. Olimkhan was shot and killed in 1810 at a place called "Alti kush". The killer was Qambar mirza from Andijan.

The reign of Umar Khan was characterized by the development of literature and art, as well as the restoration of religious foundations by pious priests, who in practice often held other powers. In the notes of the author of the given work on the history of Kokand, the names of the officials who led Kokand are given, most of them are expressed by adding the suffix "khan"biy. In 1818, Umar Khan was awarded the title of Amir-ul-muslimin for building the Jame Mosque in Kokand. In the same year, he established the title of thousand.

The era of amir Umar Khan was included in the annals of history as it formed a unique literary environment. If the addition of suffixes such as khan, bek, biy in the formation of the mentioned anthroponyms is related to the addition of real names, it can be seen that the children born from some of their illegitimate wives were called by simple names such as Madamin, Rustam, Pozil and Yodgor. In the fall of 1822, Umar Khan fell ill and died in the morning 17 days later. At noon, his son is announced as Muhammad Alikhan. 16-year-old Muhammad Ali (in some sources, 12, 14 years old) begins to manage public affairs. In this regard, the section of Ibrat's "History of Ferghana" entitled "Age of Muhammad Alikhan ibn Umar Khan" also discusses the anthroponyms whose work and activities have become history.

Even during the governorship of Mohammad Alikhan ibn Umar Khan, the naming of anthroponyms in positions is related to the pronunciation of khan and biy. After all, as the

researchers admit, from ancient times, any family, all people dreamed of having a child and leaving behind a worthy offspring. Names express the attitude of the parents to the newborn baby, that it should be beautiful, fearless, healthy, intelligent, in some cases, it should be named after the clan, tribe, ancestors to which the parents belong, that the child belongs to a certain ethnic group, that It is intended to emphasize that he is a child of an ethnic group, that his past ancestors belonged to that clan or tribe, and that the baby is their successor. However, it should be noted here that the names were influenced by the period, existing conditions and social system in some cases. Especially this can be revealed more vividly by the factual data of significant changes between the names of the citizens of the khanate period and the anthroponyms of the former shura period. In this context, the research of the anthroponyms of the city of Kokand and the historical figures mentioned in the sources related to it on a consistent scientific basis is considered one of the most important tasks.

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